

2 Translated Poems of Norberto Pannone

LOS PAJAROS SIN ALAS

Original language version

Los pájaros sin alas
se quedaron sin vuelo
bajo cielos de olvidos.
Todavía los veo
mutilar la mañana
con los ojos sin brillo.
Merodear una tarde
de bolsillos vacíos
y dormir por la calle
compartiendo el hambre
con los gnomos del frío.
Los cuervos del sueño
me truncaron al niño.
Y los hombres impíos
se olvidaron del canto,
la campana del patio
y del blanco atavío.
Se olvidaron del himno.
Andará la promesa
asustando a mi niño.
los valientes de turno,
le darán un mendrugo
al llegar los comicios.
Los pájaros sin alas,
se quedaron sin vuelo
en un cielo de olvidos.

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BIRDS WITHOUT WINGS

© English Translation by Marián Muiños - España

Birds without wings
have lost their flight
in forgotten skies.
I still can see them,
crippling the morning

with their brightless eyes.
Prowling aimlessly,
the empty-pocketed evening,
sleeping in the streets,
sharing their hunger
with the winter gnomes.
Those ravens of dreams
cut short my child.
And merciless men
have forgotten the song,
the playground bell,
and the white school apron.
They've forgotten the anthem.
The promise must be
still haunting my child.
The assumed brave ones
will give them the crusts
when polling day comes.
Birds without wings
have lost their flight
in forgotten skies.

ALZO MI COPA

Original language version

Alzo mi copa.
En mi vino sin matiz
galopa el verso.
Busca la región de lo sublime.
Colisiona el límite
fatal de la poesía
y el cristal se rompe,
derramando la vid.
Mi sueño permanece
aún austero.
Me requiebran
de ausencias
tus recuerdos.
...y bebo.

I RAISE MY GLASS

English Translation by Germain Droogenbroodt – Stanley Barkan

I raise my glass.
In my colourless wine,
gallops the verse.

It seeks the region of the sublime,
but collides with the fatal
limit of poetry,
and the glass shatters,
spilling the wine.
My dream remains
still austere.
The memory
of your absence
breaks in me.
. . . and I drink.

Bio:

Norberto Pannone was born in Junín, Buenos Aires Province, Argentina, on April 13, 1943. He is a philosopher, psychobiophysicist, poet, writer, essayist, novelist, lecturer, and cultural manager. He holds a Master's degree in Parapsychology from the Serge Reynaud de la Ferrière University of Buenos Aires.

Pannone studied scriptwriting for radio and television at the Argentine Association of Television and Radio Journalists (APTRA) under Professor Luis Buero, and later pursued studies at the Argentine Notarial University (UNA), specializing in copyright law.

For six consecutive years he served as President of the Junín branch of the Argentine Society of Writers (SADE). From 2005 to 2008 he was Vice-President and member of the National Board of Directors of SADE. He has also served as Assistant Professor in the Copyright Law department at the Argentine Notarial University.

He is President in Argentina of **ASOLAPO Argentina**, a branch of ASOLAPO International (Latin American Association of Poets, Writers, and Artists), headquartered in Cusco, Peru.

Pannone has published fifteen books across several literary genres. He is also the creator and director of the international blog **Música Histórica** and the blog of **ASOLAPO Argentina**.